

Rethinking digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe

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Executive Summary

The ReCreating Europe Training Toolkit was created in order to disseminate resources created by the project and engage stakeholders into validating research results through engagement with the authors. Embedded into the project website, the toolkit was developed based on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles and includes a variety of materials, from reports to videos of workshops created by the project partners. The toolkit serves as a discovery tool; without hosting the resources it provides the user with an easy way to search for and access links to find the resources should they be interested. Special metadata, such as short descriptions, intended audience, discipline, etc., has been created to make the search within the toolkit more refined and resources more findable.

This deliverable elaborates on the methodology and principles used for the development of the tool, its structure and content.

1. Introduction

This deliverable (D7.4) – Training Toolkit – depicts the purpose, methodology and principles behind the development of the ReCreating Europe Training Toolkit (hereinafter referred to as “the toolkit”), a discovery tool for all project’s and partners’ resources of various formats that can be used and reused for training and learning purposes by the project’s stakeholders.

The toolkit was initially imagined as an element of the Stakeholders’ platform. As the website progressed overall in a Stakeholder-focused way of presenting activities and resources, the toolkit has been assigned a separate space under project’s resources and can be assessed through this link:

<https://www.recreating.eu/training-toolkits/>

Figure 1: Training toolkit website and logo

2. Purpose

The toolkit was developed to serve two main purposes: training & dissemination, and engagement.

As a simple tool, the toolkit is a method of attracting users – relevant stakeholders – to the resources that correspond to their interests and needs. It provides an easy way to locate relevant material among all the resources produced by the project.

The toolkit also represents a way to get these users involved in conversations based on the resources relevant to them. Should the users of the tool have questions and/or comments, they are encouraged to get in touch with the authors, and the toolkit provides a way for them to do so by redirecting the user to the page of the Work Package (WP) responsible for the resource (where the contact details of WP leaders can be found).

Figure 2: Redirection to WP page on the website

3. Methodology and principles

The toolkit has been designed to serve as a discovery tool; while it does not store training resources, it contains the necessary metadata and links to the repositories in which these resources are stored. Embedded into the project website, the toolkit operates under FAIR principles and ensures resources contained in it are easily findable and accessible.

Findability

The toolkit is designed to increase the findability of the ReCreating Europe project's (and partners') resources. As such, all the resources produced by the project are stored on Zenodo, a searchable repository where they are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier, filled with rich metadata. Video resources are stored on YouTube, where significant efforts are made to ensure metadata assigned to each video allows for it to be easily found by the users (for example, by including accurate title and full description including participant names and affiliations). Based on the metadata assigned to each resource, entries in the toolkit are created to reflect this metadata and increase the resource's findability through the embedded filter options.

Figure 3: Zenodo entry with metadata

The screenshot shows a Zenodo entry for 'D2.5 Interim report on case studies' dated July 5, 2021. The entry includes the authors (Ferri, Delia; Martinelli, Arianna; Rossello, Giulia; Serra, M.Laura) and project member(s) (Donnellan, Katie). The description details the project's focus on stakeholder perspectives on the European copyright regulatory framework. The entry has 147 views and 78 downloads. It is indexed in OpenAIRE. The publication date is July 5, 2021, and the DOI is 10.5281/zenodo.5069359. The keywords are 'visual impairment' and 'copyright'. The grant is the European Commission, specifically 'reCreating Europe - Rethinking digital'. A red arrow points to the 'Publication date' field.

Accessibility

To ensure the resources can be easily accessed, the toolkit includes easy-access links to where the resources are stored. For the duration of the project, these links will be continuously checked and corrected when necessary by website moderators and the WP7 team. The metadata for the resources is included in the toolkit and not directly linked to the repositories where the data is stored, allowing for the metadata to be accessible even if the resources themselves are for some reason no longer available.

Figure 4: Access links to resources

The screenshot shows the ReCreating Europe website navigation menu with options: ABOUT, STAKEHOLDERS, ACTIVITIES & RESOURCES, NEWS & EVENTS, and NEWSLETTER. Below the menu, there are filter sections for 'Discipline' (with 'copyright law' selected), 'Format' (with 'Report' selected), and 'Access link' (with 'Zenodo' selected and highlighted by a red arrow).

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Interoperability

The principle of interoperability was taken into consideration during the toolkit development process through the formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation in the use of metadata. This includes specialized vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.

Figure 5: Metadata display example for a resource in the toolkit

The screenshot shows a web page with the following structure:

- Header:** ReCreating Europe logo, navigation menu (ABOUT, STAKEHOLDERS, ACTIVITIES & RESOURCES, NEWS & EVENTS, NEWSLETTER), and social media icons (email, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn).
- Title:** Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU
- Date:** January 21, 2022 /
- Language:** English
- Author(s):** Giulia Priora, Caterina Sganga
- Author(s) affiliation:** Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
- Keywords:** GLAM, cultural heritage
- Intended audience:** GLAM, policy makers
- Discipline:** copyright law
- Format:** Report
- Access link:** Zenodo
- Description:** The work presented in this report responds to the growing need for a sector-specific analysis of European digital copyright law vis-à-vis cultural heritage institutions (CHIs). The research carried out within Task 5.1 – European legal framework for GLAM industries: from closure to Openness of the reCreating Europe's Work Package (WP) 5 dedicated to Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAM) aims to deliver a comprehensive legal mapping of EU and national copyright provisions impacting the sector. This report is the first result of such endeavor.
- Would you like to discuss details with the authors? Please, reach out here:** WPS
- Share this entry:** Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Email

Reusability

The ReCreating Europe project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 870626. As such, all public resources produced by the project are assigned the CC-BY 4.0 license, allowing anyone to reuse them freely with attribution of the authors. The toolkit only contains resources under such license.

Figure 6: License display on Zenodo

Figure 7: License display on YouTube

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4. Structure

The toolkit has been designed to display resources and their short description on the left, as well as the search function on the right.

The list of resources and their description allows anyone who is interested to explore the resources freely. The short description has been created for each resource to allow the user to understand quickly whether it is of interest to them. To get access to more metadata and access links, the user can click on the “read more” button, which opens a page with detailed information on the resource.

Figure 8: Example of how to proceed to more metadata of a particular resource

The screenshot shows the ReCreating Europe website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for ABOUT, STAKEHOLDERS, ACTIVITIES & RESOURCES, NEWS & EVENTS, and NEWSLETTER, along with social media icons for email, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and LinkedIn. The main content area features a resource card titled "Vulnerable Groups and the Right to Culture: Challenges in a Digital World". The card includes a short description and a "Read more" link, which is highlighted with a red arrow. To the right of the resource card is a search bar labeled "Search (type in one word)" and an "Author list" section with checkboxes next to the names of the authors: Abeer Pervaiz, Alessandro Nuvolari, Arianna Martinelli, Athina Papadopoulou, Bartolomeo Meletti, Caterina Sganga, and Cecile Deniard.

Figure 9: Short description of the resource within the toolkit

The screenshot shows the ReCreating Europe website interface with the "Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive – An EU Copyright Reform Resource" selected. The interface includes a navigation menu and social media icons. The resource card is expanded to show the "Description" section, which is highlighted with a red arrow. The description text reads: "The Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market (CDSM) entered into force on 7 June 2019. It should have been transposed by Member States into national law by 7 June 2021. Only 3 Member States have met this deadline. The Directive is a complex piece of legislation, 34 pages long. The most contested Article 17 is introduced by 11 recitals (61-71) and covers in 10 dense sections new obligations by 'online content-sharing service providers', a new class of services that communicate to the public copyright content uploaded by their users. It is likely that we will see widely diverging implementations, and decades of references to the Court of Justice of the European Union, which is already suffering from copyright overload. This resource, developed in collaboration with reCreating Europe (an EU H2020 project), offers an independent academic perspective on the implementation of the directive, continuing previous work on the legislative process." There is also an "Access link" section with a bullet point for "CREATe Website".

However, for users looking for more specific resources, the search function has been developed. The function is linked to the metadata of each resource. By ticking the relevant boxes and then “filter”, the user can limit the search criteria. The resources displayed will include only those with the relevant metadata. The following search criteria have been included:

- Language
- Keyword(s)
- Author(s)
- Intended audience

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- Discipline
- Format

The user can also perform the search by typing any relevant word into the “Search” box. The search will display any results that include the search word in their title and/or description.

Figure 10: A view of the free-text search function within the toolkit

Vulnerable Groups and the Right to Culture: Challenges in a Digital World → Search (type in one word)

Search here in titles or descriptions...

Author list

- Abeer Pervaiz
- Alessandro Nuvolari
- Arianna Martinelli

5. Resources

The resources included in the toolkit currently contain relevant project deliverables, presentation slides, videos of project workshops & webinars, and blogposts. However, the format of the resources that could be included in the toolkit has intentionally not been limited to the above-mentioned, in order to allow any useful and relevant resource to be included.

The toolkit is a living tool, and will be continuously updated and populated by WP7 throughout the project. While only some non-project resources are currently included, project partners will continue to engage users and other projects to ensure relevant work is displayed.

As of 24 January 2022 the toolkit includes:

- 2 blogposts
- 16 reports
- 6 videos
- 3 webinars
- 1 workshop

The main function of the toolkit is creating an easy way to find and use resources created by the project and no resources will be created after the project completion. The toolkit will remain active but will not require special maintenance after the project is finalised. It will be maintained as part of the ReCreating Europe website.

6. Conclusions

As a living tool, the ReCreating Europe Training Toolkit was created as a way to engage relevant stakeholders into discussing the research results produced by the project, and make these results easily-findable across multiple platforms where they are stored. The toolkit was designed based on FAIR principles, and is constructed with a simple structure to allow resources to be filtered and searchable by word.

The Training Toolkit offers several benefits to the project. In line with the aims of WP7, it will assist in the dissemination of project outputs amongst relevant stakeholders, helping to ensure that such resources are utilised by their intended audience. Yet the toolkit will also be a valuable asset to the project as a whole,

offering a platform to showcase all project and partner's outputs both for the duration of the project and beyond.

